

A study to assess the effect of Structured Teaching Programme on knowledge regarding ICDS among Anganwadi Workers in a selected District of Delhi

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ABSTRACT: Background: In India, Integrated Child Development Services were first implemented in October 1975. Integrated Child Development Services are provided in Anganwadi Centers through the Anganwadi Workers. Anganwadi Worker's knowledge about ICDS is directly linked to the ultimate outcome of the ICDS scheme. Therefore, the aim of the study was to assess the effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programme in terms of knowledge regarding ICDS among Anganwadi Workers.

Materials and methods: A Pre-experimental one group pre-test post-test design was adopted in quantitative approach. A total of 100 AWWs working in ICDS-Prem Nagar Project were selected using total enumerative sampling technique. Data was collected through structured knowledge questionnaire (KR20 - 0.8) in June-2022. On Day-1, Pre-test followed by Structured Teaching Programme on ICDS was administered. On Day-7, Post-test was conducted.

Results: Pre-test study results showed that only 3% AWWs had excellent knowledge, 45% had good knowledge, 40% had average knowledge and 12% had below average knowledge regarding ICDS. After intervention, Post-test scores improved significantly. Pre-test mean±SD was 16.82±4.085 and Post-test mean±SD was 24.29±3.586. The mean post-test knowledge score was higher than the mean pre-test score with mean difference of 7.47, which was found to be statistically significant (Z= 13.739) at p<0.05. No significant association was found between the pre-test knowledge level of the AWWs and selected socio-demographic variables at p<0.05.

Conclusion: Based on the findings of the study it can be concluded that structured teaching programme on ICDS was significantly effective in enhancing the knowledge among Anganwadi workers.

Keywords: *Effectiveness, STP, AWWs, ICDS, Knowledge*

Abbreviations: AWWs - anganwadi workers, ICDS- Integrated Child Development Services, STP- Structured Teaching Programme

I. INTRODUCTION

Growth of nation depends upon the health of children. One of the crucial elements in determining a child's health is the pattern of his growth and development, which extends throughout their life cycle [1].

Integrated child development services program is a centrally backed scheme of Government of India and one of the world's biggest community-based programme to deal with the gaps and demanding situations associated with malnutrition amongst children of 0-6 years of age with unique cognizance on children younger than three years, pregnant ladies and lactating women [2].

It is the foremost image of country's commitment to its children and nursing women, as a response to the mission of providing pre-school non-formal education on one hand and breaking the vicious cycle of malnutrition, morbidity, decreased gaining knowledge of capability and mortality on the other [3].

Objectives of the Scheme are:

- to improve the nutritional and health status of children in the age-group 0-6 years;
- to lay the foundation for proper psychological, physical and social development of the child;
- to reduce the incidence of mortality, morbidity, malnutrition and school dropout;
- to achieve effective co-ordination of policy and implementation amongst the various departments to promote child development; and
- to enhance the capability of the mother to look after the normal health and nutritional needs of the child through proper nutrition and health education [2].

The ICDS Scheme offers a package of six services, viz.

- Supplementary Nutrition
- Pre-school non-formal education
- Nutrition & health education
- Immunization
- Health check-up and
- Referral services

Anganwadi worker functions at the grass root level and she is the first contact to the community from the health sector. Her trustworthiness is important to provide comprehensive care to the target group [4].

Anganwadi Worker's level of knowledge about the various services like proper nutrition, immunization etc. plays an important role related to her performance in the Anganwadi centres. Being a key functionary, her performance and profile (level of educational qualifications, training, skills etc.) is linked to the ultimate outcome of the ICDS scheme [5].

Though government is spending lot of money on ICDS programme but impact is very ineffective. Most of the studies were concentrated on the nutritional and health status of the beneficiaries of ICDS. Less focus was shifted over to assess the knowledge and awareness among anganwadi worker regarding recommended ICDS programme, who are actually the main resource person. The output of the ICDS scheme is to a great extent dependant on the profile of the key functionary i.e., the anganwadi worker, her qualification, experience, skills, attitude, training etc. The Anganwadi Worker should be self-sufficient to deliver services under Integrated Child Development Programme [6].

Once we ascertain the level of knowledge of anganwadi workers, we will be able to devise comprehensive strategies to improve the knowledge of anganwadi workers. Based on the specific knowledge deficiencies, effective interventions like educational program for imparting knowledge regarding ICDS among anganwadi workers can be developed.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To assess the pre-test knowledge regarding Integrated Child Development Services among anganwadi workers.
2. To develop and administer structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding Integrated Child Development Services to anganwadi workers.
3. To assess the post-test knowledge regarding Integrated Child Development Services among anganwadi workers.
4. To evaluate the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding Integrated Child Development Services among anganwadi workers.
5. To determine the association of pre-test knowledge of the anganwadi workers with selected socio-demographic variables.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS:

- **H₁**- The post-test knowledge score of anganwadi workers regarding Integrated Child Development Services will be significantly higher than the pre-test knowledge score after the administration of structured teaching program, as assessed by the structured knowledge questionnaire at 0.05 level of significance.
- **H₂**- There will be significant association between the pre-test knowledge score of anganwadi workers regarding Integrated Child Development Services and selected demographic variables at 0.05 level of significance.

DELIMITATIONS

The study was delimited to:

1. anganwadi workers who were present during the data collection time.
2. anganwadi workers who were working in the anganwadi centers of ICDS-Prem Nagar Project only.
3. components of Integrated Child Development Services only.

II. METHODOLOGY

For the study, quantitative approach and one group pre-test post-test research design was adopted to achieve the objectives of the study.

Independent variable: Structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding Integrated Child Development Services.

Dependent variable: Knowledge level of anganwadi workers regarding Integrated Child Development Services.

Extraneous variables: Age, educational level, marital status and years of experience as an anganwadi worker.

Setting of the study: Anganwadi Centers of Prem Nagar ICDS Project, North-West District, Delhi

Population, Sample, and Sampling Technique

100 Anganwadi workers working in Anganwadi centers of Prem Nagar ICDS project, North-West District, Delhi were selected using non probability, total enumerative sampling which is also known as, consecutive sampling.

Sample size for the present study was calculated using Cochran's Formula at 95% of C.I. and 10% of sampling error.

Inclusion criteria

The study sample included anganwadi workers:

1. who were available during the period of study.
2. working in anganwadi centers of ICDS-Prem Nagar Project, Delhi.

Selection of the tool

For the present study, tool for the data collection was a Structured Knowledge Questionnaire to assess knowledge regarding Integrated Child Development Services among anganwadi workers. Paper and pencil method was used to administer the tool.

The tool was divided into two sections:

Section I: Demographic variables such as age, marital status, educational status and years of experience as an anganwadi worker.

Section II: Structured knowledge questionnaire consisting of 30 questions related to assessment of knowledge regarding Integrated Child Development Services.

- Every question with correct answer was given 1 mark and wrong answer was given 0 mark.
- Maximum score - 30
- Minimum score – 0

Interpretation of scores:

Level of knowledge	:	Range of scores
Excellent	:	24 - 30
Good	:	18 - 23
Average	:	12 - 17
Below Average	:	0 – 11

To ensure the validity of the tool, it was given to 11 experts selected from the fields of Community Health, Pediatrics Nursing and Medical Surgical Nursing. The experts were chosen on the basis of their clinical expertise, experience, qualification and interest in the problem area. Their suggestions were incorporated in the tool. Final tool consisted of 30 items.

The reliability of the tool was established using Kuder-Richardson Formula 20 (KR-20) and it was found to be 0.80 (80%).

Ethical Considerations

Ethical permission was obtained from the ethical committee of St. Stephen's Hospital and administrative approval for the final study was obtained from the Competent Authority, Department of Women and Child Development, Govt. of NCT of Delhi. Written informed consent was also obtained from the subjects after explaining the purpose of the study. The confidentiality of their responses and anonymity was assured throughout the study.

Procedure for final data collection

Study was conducted from 13/06/2022 to 02/07/2022 on 100 anganwadi workers of ICDS-Prem Nagar project, North-West District, Delhi. Self-introduction was given and purpose of the study was explained to anganwadi workers. Confidentiality of their response was assured. Formal informed consent was obtained from the subjects who met the inclusion criteria. On day 1, pre-test was administered using a structured knowledge questionnaire on Integrated Child Development Services. Subjects took around 25-30 minutes to fill the questionnaire. A Structured Teaching Programme on Integrated Child Development Services was administered to the subjects immediately after the pre-test, followed by the post-test on the 7th day using the same structured knowledge questionnaire.

III. RESULTS

The findings reveal that, majority 61% of AWWs were in the age group of 26-40years, 52% were educated upto graduation and above, 91% were married and 81% were having experience of 11-15years as AWW.

Figure 1: Bar graph depicting Percentage Distribution of Pre-test and Post-test knowledge scores of the Anganwadi Workers.

Figure-1 showing the analysis data related to knowledge of Anganwadi Workers suggested that the maximum 45% scored between 18-23 in the pre-test of knowledge regarding ICDS and post test scores show that 67% scored between 24-30 in the post test of knowledge regarding ICDS.

Table 2 Pre-test & Post test knowledge score

N=100							
Group	Observed Score range	Mean	Mean Difference	Median	Standard Deviation	'Z' Value at p<0.05	Critical 'Z' value at p<0.05
PRE TEST	04-25	16.82	7.47	17	4.085	13.739*	2.00
POST TEST	15-30	24.29		25	3.586		

The table 2 shows the summary of statistical results that pre-test knowledge mean is 16.82 and after structured teaching programme post test mean rises to 24.29 to check whether this rise in Mean knowledge score is statistically significant or not, researcher applied 'Z' test. Since calculated z value is more than the table value at p<0.05 level of significance, there is significant increase in Mean Knowledge score after intervention. Therefore, the researcher can conclude that structured teaching programme was effective. Hence, H_{01} is rejected and H_1 is accepted.

Table-3 Association with demographic variables

N=100								
S.no.	Selected Variables	Excellent Knowledge	Good Knowledge	Average Knowledge	Below Average Knowledge	Chi-Square value (χ^2)	Df	Table Value
		Frequency (f)	Frequency (f)	Frequency (f)	Frequency (f)			
1.	Age (in years):					9.761 ^{NS}	9	16.92
	18 -25 years	0	2	0	0			
	26 - 40 years	3	29	24	5			
	41 - 50 years	0	11	16	6			
	51 - 60 years	0	3	0	1			
2.	Education:					11.738 ^{NS}	6	12.59
	Upto 8 th	-	-	-	-			
	Upto 10 th	0	3	6	6			
	Upto 12 th	1	16	14	2			
	Graduation and above	2	26	20	4			
1.	Marital Status:					3.096 ^{NS}	6	12.59
	Married	3	39	38	11			
	Unmarried	0	4	1	0			
	Widow	0	2	1	1			
	Divorcee	-	-	-	-			
2.	Years of Experience as an Anganwadi Worker:					6.131 ^{NS}	9	16.92
	≤5 years	0	2	3	1			
	6-10 years	0	7	3	1			
	11-15 years	3	36	33	9			
	16-20 years	0	0	1	1			
	20 years and above	-	-	-	-			

*NS-Not Significant

Since, calculated chi-square value is less than table value at p<0.05 level of significance so there was no significant association between pre-test knowledge score and demographic variable found. Hence, H_2 is rejected and H_{02} is accepted.

IV. DISCUSSION

The findings of the present study have been discussed in relation to the observation made by other studies which the investigator reviewed.

The findings of the present study were found similar to the study findings of **Sharma KK.(2021)** who conducted a study to assess the effectiveness of self-instructional module regarding assessment and prevention of protein energy malnutrition in children under five years of age among anganwadi workers at selected ICDS centre at Jaipur using pre-experimental pre-test-post-test research design approach in 2021. 50 anganwadi workers were selected for the study using non-probability convenient sampling technique. Demographic scale and structured interview schedule were formulated to assess the effectiveness of self-instructional module. The findings of the study showed that overall mean post test knowledge score was significantly higher than the pre -test knowledge score with a mean difference of 11.29. Hence, the self-instructional module was effective [7]. In the present study also, post test mean score was more than the pre-test mean score with a mean difference of 7.47 and the structured teaching programme was also found effective.

Similar findings were also found in the study conducted by **Sivadas S.(2020)** which was aimed to assess the effectiveness of planned teaching programme on knowledge regarding national nutritional programme for children among 40 anganwadi workers from selected Anganwadi centre at Mangalore rural area in 2020. One group pre-test and post-test pre-experimental design was used. Study results revealed that the overall mean post-test knowledge score regarding national nutritional program for children (30.25 ± 5.88) was significantly higher than overall mean pre-test knowledge score regarding national nutritional program for children (16.95 ± 4.66) and the obtained 't' value was 22.96, which was higher than the table value and there was no significant association between the pre-test knowledge score with the demographic variables of anganwadi worker [8]. These results coincide with the findings of the present study.

However, some researchers were able to find out association between the knowledge score and the demographic variables which are in contrary to this study. **Parmar M, Patel S, Rathod S, Patel N, Ninama K.(2014)** conducted a study aimed to assess the knowledge of anganwadi workers regarding ICDS in September 2014. Study results showed that educational level of anganwadi workers was positively associated with the correct knowledge score about ICDS scheme [9].

Similarly, **Ranjan R, Das M, Das S.(2018)** conducted a study to assess the level of knowledge among anganwadi workers regarding services of ICDS in Sitamarhi, Bihar during the period 18th December 2017 to 30th March 2018. Results showed that education level and training of anganwadi workers showed significant association with the knowledge regarding ICDS components [10].

Many other researchers also found the similar results which showed that teaching programmes are effective in increasing knowledge of anganwadi workers regarding ICDS. Some were able to find association between knowledge and demographic variable especially with education level.

V. CONCLUSION

The conclusions drawn from the study are as follows: -

The main objective of the study was to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding Integrated Child Development Services among anganwadi workers. Mean post-test knowledge score of the samples was significantly higher than the mean pre-test knowledge score with a mean difference of 7.47. The calculated 'Z' value of 13.739 was greater than the table value 2.000 at $p < 0.05$ level of significance, which showed that structured teaching programme was found to be effective in increasing the knowledge level of anganwadi workers regarding ICDS. No significant association was found between the pre-test knowledge score of anganwadi workers regarding Integrated Child Development Services and the selected demographic variables as calculated Chi-Square value was lower than the table value at $p < 0.05$.

Hence, it is concluded that Structured teaching programme is effective in increasing knowledge of anganwadi Workers regarding Integrated Child Development services.

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